

Microstructure generation of carbon fiber reinforced polyamide 6 by a generative adversarial network (GAN) based on μ CT data

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3rd generation IRTG 2078

Microstructure characterization on volumetric images

Fiber volume content (FVC)

- Elastic properties
- Density

Fiber orientation distributions

- Elastic properties
- Creep behaviour

0.105635	-0.093760	0.008141
-0.093760	0.859305	-0.104421
0.008141	-0.104421	0.035060

Fiber length distribution (FLD)

- Damage initiation
- Flow behaviour

In-situ tests

Figure 1: Force-displacement-curve for in-situ tensile test of PA6/CF sample

BUT: Low image quality of CFRP scans

- **Low contrast** between carbon fiber and polymer
- High resolution needed due to **small diameter** of carbon fiber
- Both leads to high amount of salt and pepper **noise** in CT scans

→ Generate realistic microstructures in order to understand behavior better

25 mm

25 mm

State of the art: Microstructure generation

- Conventional approach: “sphere-packing algorithms” (RSA [1], Lubachevsky-Stillinger [2], mechanical contraction [3], Torquato-Jiao[4])
- Problems for higher FVC or fiber curvature
- Newer, improved approaches (Schneider 2022 [5])

- Alternative: AI-based approach
- Generative adversarial networks (GANs) introduced by Goodfellow et al. in 2014 [6]

Generative adversarial network (GAN)

GAN vs. DCGAN

- Dense layers (feed-forward)
- Continuous convolution

$$(f * g)(x) := \int f(\tau)g(x - \tau)d\tau$$

10	10	10	0	0	0
10	10	10	0	0	0
10	10	10	0	0	0
10	10	10	0	0	0
10	10	10	0	0	0
10	10	10	0	0	0

*

1	0	-1
1	0	-1
1	0	-1

=

0	30	30	0
0	30	30	0
0	30	30	0
0	30	30	0

Image

3 × 3 filter

Feature map

Input data and pre-processing

1. Cutting

1024
× 1024

2. Resizing

128
× 128

3. Normalization

$2^8 = 256 \text{ values}$
 $\in [0,1] \rightarrow \in [-1,1]$

$$x_{train,new} = \frac{x_{train} - \mu_{train}}{\sigma_{train}}$$

4. Augmentation

Rotation

Mirroring

DCGAN network architecture

Additional parameters

Parameter	Chosen value
Learning rate	0.0001 , 0.0002, 0.0005
Optimizer	Adam
Loss function	BCE , Wasserstein
Batch size	32, 64, 128
Epochs	50, 100 , 150
Kernel size (convolution)	4×4 , 5×5

Loss plot

Generated images GAN

GAN_2D_bs128_lr0001 | 2023-05-15 17:26:21 | Batch Size 128 | Iteration 100

Generated images DCGAN

DCGAN_2D_bs128_lr0001 | 2023-05-15 09:55:30 | Batch Size 128 | Iteration 96

Fréchet Inception Distance (FID)

$$d(X, Y) = (\mu_X - \mu_Y)^2 + (\sigma_X - \sigma_Y)^2$$

“univariate”

$$\text{FID} = \|\mu_X - \mu_Y\|^2 - \text{Tr}(\Sigma_X + \Sigma_Y - 2\sqrt{\Sigma_X \Sigma_Y})$$

“multivariate”

X, Y : Real and fake embeddings (activation from Inception model)

μ_X and μ_Y : Magnitudes of vector X and Y

Σ_X, Σ_Y : Covariance matrix of the vectors

Frechet Inception Distance

Nearest neighbor GAN

- Based on Eukclidean distance (ED):

$$d(p, q) = \sqrt{(q_1 - p_1)^2 + (q_2 - p_2)^2}$$

Nearest neighbor DCGAN

SSIM GAN

$$SSIM(x, y) = \frac{(2\mu_x\mu_y + c_1)(2\sigma_{xy} + c_2)}{(\mu_x^2 + \mu_y^2 + c_1)(\sigma_x^2 + \sigma_y^2 + c_2)}$$

GAN

SSIM DCGAN

Discussion

- **DCGAN** reproduces **noise** more strongly
- **GAN** produces images very **close to training** data (structurally)
- Normal GAN: nearest neighbors determined with ED hardly differ from those determined with SSIM
- DCGAN: for images deviating more strongly from training data, more plausible nearest neighbors are found with SSIM (however, some results still out of line)
- SSIM value could become interesting again, especially at higher resolutions

Outlook

- Median filter for input data
- Higher resolution of input data
- More input data
- Texture quantification (Haralick entropy, etc.)
- Adaption of network for Wasserstein loss (e.g. RMS prop as optimizer)
- Binarization of input data?
- Super resolution network in front of GAN?

Thanks for your attention!

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